

DESIGN AND ANALYSIS OF LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

The coronavirus disease 19 (COVID-19) is a pathogenic viral infection which is highly transmittable which first emerged from Wuhan, China. With the increase spread of the COVID-19 and the increase death rates, the “normal” way of life changed as strict law were enforced to stop further spread and deaths. The introduction of such laws to prevent the spread of the virus changed the normal flow of education institution. Learning is a normal way of life which simulates growth and personal/ social development, most effective learning is the face-to-face learning but with the death rates on the rise and strict rule effected, the face-to –face learning was suspended for a while. The objective of this paper is to suggest an effective way of learning during and after the pandemic and also evaluate the effectiveness of the suggested system in Nigeria educational institution.

Keywords: Learning Management System (LMS), COVID-19, online learning

INTRODUCTION

COVID-19 epidemic is a major disaster as it affects all ages, Ailment are transmitted through large droplet produced by infected individuals either through sneezing or coughing. COVID-19 can be transferred also either through contact with containment environment, exposure to infected Humans or Animals. The mode of the virus transmission affects all normal ways of life because it is difficulty to detect infected individual or a contaminated environment. The education institute is also affected by the COVID-19 spread because one of the ways of learning is face-to face communication which is mostly in an enclosed space.

Learning is a process of achieving knowledge, skill, and performance. Thus, learning is ultimately considered one of the fundamental pillars of society changes (Wang Y., 2015). With the development of accessible technology like the internet, important aspects of our lives including academic learning has drafted from its traditional ways, thereby, initialing E-learning or online learning has received much attention in recent years globally, with an estimated 5-7 million students now are enrolling in at least one online course each year (Allen and Jeff, 2015)

Brown and Eis (2016) identified five advantages of corporate LMS, they are; centralized learning environment to ensure consistency, tracking and reporting for enhanced performance, immediate capabilities evaluation, continuous product and service proficiency for employees who interact with customers and clients, regulatory and legal compliance.

Learning is a process of achieving knowledge, skill, and performance. Thus, learning is ultimately considered one of the fundamental pillars of society changes (Wang, 2015). Nowadays, technology has obviously made our lives easier. That means internet technology has been considered as an important medium for many aspects of our lives including academic learning. E-learning or online learning has received much attention in recent years globally, with an estimated 5-7 million students now are enrolling in at least one online course each year (Allen and Jeff, 2015). Statistically and evidently, millions of people are overlooking the cost of education and are completing their college education through distance learning (Fındık-Coşkunçay *et al.*, 2015). Formulating and executing business and higher education strategies that will improve how higher education institutions identify and mitigate these issues that are impairing their ability to execute their mission and reaching their goals are essential to the expansion and influence of the higher education institution in the community (Bailey, 2013). Moreover, without focusing on profitability, implementing an effective business strategy and business model will enable higher education institutions to operate in a manner that maximizes their resources and meet their stakeholder's expectation (Shishehchi, 2012).

Embracing and implementing business model practices should not be looked upon as a negative approach that will mitigate higher education institutions issues, but rather the conduct of leadership must be looked upon as the potential problem that may affect a higher education institution's ability to fulfill its mission and reach its goals (Al- Huang *et al*, 2020).

This study explored learning management systems as a positive contribution to education institutions economic and financial challenges and its influence on learner's decision making and accessibility to acquire their college education. Online learning and learning management systems are interconnected and are the most popular higher education trend that is making it accessible and convenient for

learners to complete their college education from anywhere in the world. Learning management systems have created a paradigm shift and is the game-changer for traditional teaching and learning at higher education institutions (Alhosban and Ismaile, 2018).

According to Adzharuddin and Lee (2013) “Learning Management System or popularly known as LMS in the community of higher institutions is an online portal that connects lecturers and students. It provides an avenue for classroom materials or activities to be shared easily”. It is also a portal that enables lecturers and students to interact out of the classroom, having discussions through forums that could otherwise take up too much of the time supposed to be spent learning in the classroom (Kaplan-Leiserson, 2015).

RELATED WORKS

The effects of the use of technology in educational institutions have been investigated for many years by studies in the field of education, which have proven and disclosed that technology can assist in various educational processes (Brown and Eis, 2016; Dermentzi *et al.*, 2016, Hung and Yyen 2010), have a positive impact on student learning support (Dyson *et al.*, 2015), and help teachers toward professional advancement and development (Manca and Raineri, 2017; Donelan, 2016). Therefore, the integration of technology into the classroom has been widely promoted and supported around the world (Cope and Ward, 2012).

The development of information and communications technology (ICT) and its utilization in learning processes has enabled learning to become more adaptable and teaching methodologies to become more flexible, thus making students more independent and self-determined, becoming responsible for learning (Goode, 2017), gaining self-regulating abilities in relation to goal setting, and becoming self-monitoring and adaptable. Such opportunities also allow teachers to promote active learning so that learning is engaging and effective (Collis, 2018), which makes them facilitators of the learning process (Huang *et al.*, 2010) and exempts them from the responsibilities of teaching alone by giving students responsibility as well (Goode, 2017). Moreover, with the development of technology, the

student-centered approach is considered the main component of flexible learning, as it empowers students and teachers to share information with each other (Lundin, 2019).

The spread of COVID-19 has also caused fear, anxiety, and various concerns among citizens around the world (NCIRD, 2020). For certain groups of people involved in education, however, it has been assumed that the level of concern observed during this period has also been influenced by factors other than COVID-19. In addition to the circumstances caused by social isolation and other personal factors, parents' concerns are assumed to have been influenced by their unpreparedness to assist their children in remote/online learning, lack of access to the necessary technology and the Internet, or the inadequacy of the technological formats used for children with special educational needs and economic difficulties (UNESCO, 2020).

According to Duraku and Hoxh (2020) “The concerns of teachers engaged in teaching processes have been observed to be related to their capacities of conducting remote/online learning due to the level of their knowledge and skills in the use of technology, their access to technology, and at-home isolation. Such concerns have been reported in particular by countries that declared an extremely low-level use of classroom technology prior to the current circumstances. In addition, requests for shifting teaching to online format have also been reported to increase the level of stress and anxiety among teachers in different parts of the world.”

Despite the current circumstances that the whole world is facing due to COVID-19, the development of the online learning process positively affects citizens by providing support to more easily overcome the isolation period. If developed based on factors that can improve the quality of education, this implementation can have positive long-term effects (Gjoshi and Kumi, 2014).

THE IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON LEARNING PROCESSES

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RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The system design will be structured with a computer science department student. This is to ensure easy dissemination of information to the entire student body. Also, upcoming events can be posted on the LMS to effectively notify the university community of scheduled events. Online forums would also be made available for academic discussions.

An LMS is indeed very feasible as it provides a larger avenue for learning in addition to rapid delivery of learning content on a scalable web-based platform. Once tested and implemented, the LMS would be updated and maintained at regular intervals.

The LMS is will be divided into basic modules. This module will support student’s assessment and grade evaluation. These are:

- Quiz
- Assignment

Other Modules that indirectly support assessment are the Forum and the Journal Modules

Already a member ? [Go and log in](#)

Registration Portal

Your username

Your email

Your password

Please confirm your password

Fig 1. Registration page

Fig 2. Student dashboard interface

Fig 3. Student registration interface

Fig 4.

MODEL EXECUTION FLOWCHART

This flow chart is mainly used to describe the realization of system functions, so as to lay the foundation for subsequent work. Therefore, it is frequently used in the field of system development. It displays the process of user identity identification and system response. Details of the flow chart is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: The flow chart of system overall function

The Realization of System Public Module

In developing the system, we set log-in module, log-out module and other public modules to achieve its function. The log-in module is taken as an example to expound the complicate realization of module functions. The system will first verify user access through the log-in module, and then set limits on log-in time. Users without any operation during the predefined log-in time are required to return to the log-in page to re-verify accounts and passwords. It simultaneously maintains the confidentiality of user ID and spares the efforts for users to perform ID identification for several times. After users are authenticated, the system will jump to the personal page. Fig. 6 shows the details of the log-in process.

Fig. 6: The flow chart of online GST tutor platforms

Course Content Management

In order to facilitate curriculum management, we unified the system pattern so that all teachers can manage the system without accepting tailor-made training. Course management should be designed to simplify operations and to render the curriculum management more accessible to teachers. For instance, we may add or edit system documents with Microsoft Word operations; we can also categorize student skills according to course materials. This management mainly involves skills of reading, listening and writing, such as separating listening practice from middle-length-to-long reading material practice and writing training. The corresponding functional process is shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7: The flow chart of course content management

DISCUSSION

Research methodology is the process of carrying out details investigation and an in-depth study of the system. Simply, it is the examination of the various parts of the system as to gather the necessary facts with a view to use the resulting information to design and implement a better system. The task of investigation and analysis involves fact-finding and analysis of the facts. A typical iteration process flow can be visualized as follows:

- i. System Requirements -
- ii. Development - Design and develop software based on defined requirements
- iii. Testing - Quality Assurance testing, internal and external training, documentation development
- iv. Delivery

v. Feedback

PROPOSED SYSTEM

This LSM research uses the research process and development methods. Students participated in the survey. Its development methods are divided into three parts: the Phase I is the Gathering of User requirements; Phase II is design and Phase III is development and Implementation. In Phase I, the researchers identify the purpose of the proposed system, and analyze data requirements. The next Phase is preparation flowcharts. The developed LMS is tested on small of Students and few Lecturers in order to acquire performance feedback. This stage requires a lot of reference by experts their academic fields and diagnose the system faults in order improvement the proposed system. To collect data, we use questionnaires and simple observation (with a scale of 1 to 5). A score of 5 indicates a very high argument while a score of 1 indicates poor argument. (Hilliard, 2015)

Evaluating the Effectiveness of LMS

The proposed system is of great advantage but there was noticeable demerit associated with the use of the system in Nigeria education institutions. The use of questionnaires was employed to help evaluate the reaction of users of the system in Nigeria. The parameter used were base of different faculty/ subject of learning, Users advantages and constraints of the proposed system. (Moussavi *et al.*, 2020). This methodology was adopted as student from delta state university attended online lectures during the time of the lockdown.

Fig 8: Faculty of Education

Fig. 9: Faculty of Law

Fig. 10: Faculty of Engineering

Fig. 11: Faculty of Science

DISCUSSION

Fig11 shows that student from faculty of education and law found the LMS effective while in fig. 10 faculty of science and engineering found that the proposed system isn't as effective, mostly because the practical aspect of their courses (As seen in fig and fig below)

Fig. 10: Practical-based lectures

Fig. 11: Discussion-based lectures

The proposed system introduces significant advantage of the use of learning management system for effective learning. The following are some of the advantage of the proposed system;

- i. Improve the knowledge management system
- ii. Real time learning as distance is not a barrier
- iii. Student learn at their pace; thus it is a flexible learning process
- iv. Assessment of student of possible

CONCLUSION

This research work designed and implement a learning management system to enhance tradition teaching and learning method. This research provides necessary information on student's participation and simulations on different fields of study.

In addition, the developed system will help to create a flexible learning and teaching method. This system will eliminate all restrictions, allowing individuals from all over the world to complete the courses or training they are interested in. Distance or government breaks and coronavirus pandemic will not be barer in learning.

Furthermore, the developed system will provide an overview of the E-learning aspects, attitudes and academic performance in order to provide key information to further research in similar areas. Finally, the study will provide knowledge and guidelines to policymakers, planners, students, and teachers as well as for researchers.

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